

Educational Attainments and Enrollment Ratio of Tribal in Akkalkwa Tahsil of Nandurbar District

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Abstract:

Education is one of the principal means of development of tribal people. Education helps to create opportunities of jobs and self-career development thus empowering male & female tribal population. It also helps to upgrade living standard with better health and assured resource of living. However it is well proved that educated tribal population present paper press into the levels of educational attainment & enrollment Ratio of tribal population in Akkalkua Tahsil in Nandurabar district of Maharashtra. Further it is verified encouraging and adverse factors of level of educational attainment & enrollment Ratio of the tribal population. Study is mainly based on primary and secondary source of data primary data intensive filed work. Secondary data census hand book, socio-economic Abstracts of Nandurbar districts from ongoing study it is found that the proportion educational attainments enrollment ratio in tribes in the Akkalkua tahsil selected villages at primary level, middle level, higher secondary level, state of educational attainment among the tribal is a also serious concern. Hardly 14% tribes are with primary education, less than 5% S. S. C. about 6% H.S.C. and graduation less than 2% education at facilities are very scant only Ashramshala are made available in some villages. The literacy and educational attainment is high in those villages where Ashramshala is available. It provides hostel facility and two time meal.

Key words - educational attainment, tribal, enrollment Ratio facilities etc.

Introduction:

The term ‘tribe’ is very complex to define however it is attempted to define by considering different point of views. The constitution of Indian union (Article 366) has defended the scheduled tribe as such tribes or tribal communities as or deem under article 342 to be scheduled tribe for the purpose of constitution.

Since there are close Association of education and development of the society the role of tribal in socio-economic and cultural development of her family, society and nation is significant whom tribes are not well educated education in empowers tribes.

The present study deals with educational attainment are status of tribes in Akkakua tashil. The level of educational attainment are regarded as key variables affecting present paper aims to analysis the level of educational attainment and enrollment ratio in tribes in Akkalkua tashil.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the level of educational Attainment for the selected villages for) for akkalkuwa tashil in Nandurbar district.
2. To study the levels of enrollment Ratio for the selected Villages for Akkalkua tashil in Nandurbar district.

Study Region:

The present study intends to assess the level of living in tribal population in Nandurbar district with reference to some selected tribal villages (Bardi, Surgas, vehgi, Biialighan, pippalkhuta) in Akkalkua tashil of Nandurbar district in the year at Jan, 2008.

Database & Methodology:

In order to meet these objectives, the study is mainly based on primary data. Which have been collected by conduction by intensive field work in selected five treble villages in Akkalkuwa tashil. Researcher present study use on secondary data for the district census had book, socio-economic abstract and census of India on the information on website.

Researcher has used present study use for survey method to study this problem this is survey type of research survey method is used by researcher because the researcher works with study level of education Attainment and enrollment Ratio.

Researcher has been collecting information of educational Attainment & enrollment Ratio use for questionnaire & interview method.

Table No. 1.1
Nandurbar Distractor for Akkalkuwa Tashsil
Levels of Educational Attainment at Village Level Village Name

Village Name.																
Sr.NO	Sector	Suragas			Bardi			Pimpalkhuta			Bijaligavan			Vehgi		
		T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F
1	Primary (4th)	13.9	17.	10.	15	18.	11	11.	13	10	17.	20.	14.	5.8	11.7	0
2	Middle (8th)	2.63	2.9	2.2	5.3	7.6	10.	3.1	5.4	0.6	2.7	4.0	1.4	2.9	5.88	0
3	SSC (10th)	4.51	5.2	3.7	4.0	4.8	2.7	2.5	4.2	0.6	4.1	5.4	2.8	2.9	2.9	3.03
4	HSC (12th)	5.63	6.7	4.5	2.5	3.1	1.5	4.1	7.2	0.6	2.7	5.4	0	2.9	0	6.06
5	Graduation	1.87	3.7	0	0.7	1.3	0	0	0	0	1.3	2.7	0	1.4	2.9	0
6	Post-Graduation	.37	.74	0	.77	1.38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4	0	0
	Average	5.78	7.3	4.2	5.7	7.3	5.1	4.3	6.0	2.4	5.6	7.5	3.7	3.5	4.7	1.82

(Source: Fieldwork January 2008)

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Levels of Educational Attainment at Village Level

1. Primary Education Level:-

In this section the attempt is made to analyze the levels of educational attainment among tribal in 5 village's viz., Surgas, Bardi, Pimpalkhuta, Bijaligavhan and Vehgi. It is found that the proportion of tribal persons with primary education at village level varies from nearly 5.88% in Vehgi to a maximum of 17.36% in Bijaligavhan. It is a very low level of educational attainment even

at primary level. It seems that where or nearby the village Ashramshala is made available, there the proportion of tribal people with primary education is relatively high than those villages where there is not. For example, the Ashramshala was available in Bardi and Surgas and Zillah Parishad School and in Ashramshala children are provided hostel as well as food free of cost with which they are attracted to school. With this pretext they get education also. It is also noticed that male children even among the tribal are given preference over the females. In each village the Primary level educational attainment is much higher than the female children. It is important to note that the Vehgi 11 % males with primary education but none was among the females.

2. Middle Educational Level

The proportion of middle level are of 8th standard level is hardly 2 to 5% in the villages of study area. The proportion of males is relatively

Much higher than the females. There is wide disparity between males and females at primary and middle levels.

I. SSC Level

At SSC level also hardly 2 to 5% tribal are 10th pass. At this SSC level, the proportion of females nowhere more than the males. The

disparity between male and female is quite high.

3. Higher Secondary Level

At HSC level or 12th standard level, it is further found that the proportion of tribe's with HSC varies between 2 and less than 6%. The proportion of males that varies between 0 and about 7%. So the disparity at this level is also quite high.

4. Graduation Level

Except Surgas, Bijaligavhan and Vehgi nowhere the proportion is even 1 %. And in all the cases in all the 5 villages' no single tribal women was graduate. And question of post-graduation is far away.

5. Post-Graduation Level

At post-graduation level only in Surgas, Bardi and Vehgi where the proportion is less than 1 to 1 and 5%. But none of the women are graduate and post graduate in these villages.

All this very clearly indicates that where there is Ashramshala or Zillah Parishad School the proportion of tribal is relatively higher than where Very high. But after HSC i.e., graduation and post graduate level only very few males are going outside for higher education but females are left in the villages. This is due to geographical distance, poverty and insecurity about the female girls. If this facility of school is extended to each village within one or 2 km distance and college near by the villages at some central point, it can enhance their levels of educational attainment which is necessary condition for their social and economic development.

Enrollment Ratio:

Enrollment of children of any society reflects the development and understanding of the people regarding educational attainment. The parents who are conscious about education of their children, they make it tangible at any cost to send them to school. This is truer in case of higher caste children particularly of Brahmins. But nowadays the other people (other than the Brahmins) have also understood the importance of education but their poverty, illiteracy, some social problems entail them to withdraw, their children from school and in such a case the dropout rate is quite high. For example, the enrollment ratio varies from 35.29% in Vehgi to near about 60% in Bardi. On an average more the 40% children are not being enrolled even at primary level. On an average 45% children are

not being enrolled this may be because of geographical Of 6-10 age groups all should get enrolled in the school but it has not happened even in 2008.

Table 1.2
Akkalkuwa Tashsil Nandurbar District
Enrollment Ratio at Village Level

S r. N o .	EDUC ATION	PRI MAR Y	M .P	SECO NDR Y	H. S	GRAD UTION	P. G.
		I-IV	V- VI I	VIII- X	XI - XI I	XIII- XV	X V I- X V II
	AGE GROU P	6 TO 10	11 TO 14	15 TO 18	17 TO 18	19 TO 21	22 TO 24
	Village Name	69.9	58.7	40	20	8.57	0
1	BARDI		5				
2	SURGAS	63.15	65.71	47.61	88.6	12.5	5
3	VERGI	35.29	33.3	25	0	0	0
4	BIJALIGAVHAN	48.38	33.3	35.71	55.5	0	0
5	PIMPALKHUTA	60	79.6	70	53.3	4.54	0
	AVERAGE	53.34	54.65	43.66	43.1	5.12	1

(Source: Fieldwork January 2008)

1. Higher Primary Level

At Higher Primary level, in Vehgi and Bijaligavhan hardly 1/3 of the children between 11 and 14 are being enrolled and in Bardi nearly 59%, Surgas 66% and Pimpalkhuta 79%. On an average 46% children remain outside the school. At secondary level nearly 48% children of 15 to 16 age group are attending the school.

2. Secondary Level

At secondary level, the enrollment has declined from 54% at higher primary to hardly 44% at secondary level. The minimum enrollment was 25% in Vehgi village and the maximum was 70% in Pimpalkhuta. This decline is due to non-availability of the secondary schools within the reachable distance. Moreover the communication system is very poor.

3. Higher Secondary Level

At higher secondary level also the enrollment is hardly 43%. It is very surprising to note that none was enrolled for higher secondary level of education. But in Surgas village where Ashramshala was available which provide food and accommodation to the students who were enrolled. The enrollment was as high as 87%, whereas in Bardi it was 20%. The disparities in enrollment are very sharp. This high percentage of enrollment at higher secondary level in Surgas village, in Bijali gavhan and Pimpalkhuta is because of the accumulation of failure students. High percentage does not mean that enrollment has increased.

4. Graduation Level

At Graduation level, on an average the enrollment is hardly 5% and 95% dropout. In Vehgi and Bijaligavhan none was enrolled for graduation. It was only in Bardi, Surgas and Pimpalkhuta where a few were enrolled for it otherwise the condition after higher secondary is serious one. Neither the facility nor their economic condition allows to get enrolled.

5. Post-Graduation Level

Hardly 1 % that is too in Surgas village, tribals were enrolled for post-graduation who must have been taking education outside the village otherwise except Surgas nowhere any person was found enrolled for post-graduation. As a whole, it is intended that until unless they will attain higher level of education, heir living condition cannot be improved.

Conclusion

It is inferred that the tribal literacy has increased 36.79% to 55.20% in 1991 and 2001. Similarly, rural literacy from 32.67% to 55.30% and urban 64.58% to 74.20%. The female literacy has been increasing at a bit faster rate. Male-female as well as rural-urban disparities among the tribes have also been declined in the state of Maharashtra. The disparity between tribal and non-tribal has been reduced from 0.323 in 1991 to 0.232 in 2001.

At village level the male-female disparity is very high. The overall male-female literacy rates are also quite low because of poverty and very poor communication system. The enrollment rate at primary level is about 54%, which comes down to 43% at higher secondary level and at graduation level is just 5%. The dropout rate is very high. The educational attainment among the tribes at primary level is hardly 13%, at middle 2.6%, at SSC 4.5%, at HSC 5.6% and at graduation 1.88%, the educational attainment after primary is almost negligible. This is all due to their absolute poverty, unemployment, poor roads and communication system, non-availability of schools in the villages, social insecurity for girls, etc are some of the reasons of their low literacy, high male, female disparity and high dropout ratio. It can be improved by increasing their purchasing power by improved by increasing their purchasing power by providing employment medical services and other attention needs for raising their living standards.

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